

TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE BASED ON FICTION

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Annotation: The article is concerned with the features of application authentic texts in teaching Russian as a foreign language. Reading poetry texts activates the assimilation of grammatical material, contributes to the formation of speech skills of students. Adequate understanding of such works is achieved through a carefully designed system pre-, near-, end- text exercises.

Key words: reading, authentic texts, poetry texts, Russian as a foreign language.

An important component in teaching the Russian language is the assimilation of cultural patterns through literary texts. Many linguists, including Eduard Sepir, argue that "language is a symbolic guide to understanding culture" [1, p. 162], which only confirms Humboldt's ideas, which found its extreme expression in the Sepir–Worf hypothesis. According to these concepts, language and thinking are closely related [2, p. 7]. Indeed, language reflects the culture and thinking of a particular nation or a particular people. The language is closely connected with national psychology, with the identity of the people, with stereotypes of thinking, traditions. "Each language reflects the culture of the people who speak it," wrote L. V. Shcherba. There are about three thousand languages on Earth, and each language has its own characteristics and structural specifics. According to ethnologist K. Levi-Strauss, "the originality of each culture lies, first of all, in its own way of solving problems, promising placement of values that are common to all people. Only their significance is never the same in different cultures" [3, p. 72].

Language is a mirror of culture. When learning Russian by a foreign student, one of the important aspects is penetration into culture, its understanding and mastering. And nothing will show our culture better than fiction, which has been used by more than one generation of the Russian people.

So why should teachers of Russian as a foreign language include the study of fiction as an obligatory part of their educational program? There are a number of objective reasons for this.

Firstly, a teacher in any environment (kindergarten, school or university) faces a difficult task – to choose the right artistically valuable and significant texts that will contain information about the culture of our country. They should not only be filled with the cultural component of the life of the Russian people, but they should also be familiar to the entire language team and make up background knowledge of all native speakers of the Russian language. On the other hand, reading such texts enriches students' lexical and grammatical competencies, helps them develop other types of speech activity. In addition, reading literary texts develops students' analytical thinking and creative skills.

Secondly, it is only when there is motivation that high-quality education arises. Methodologists believe that motivation and interest are considered the most important conditions for quality education. It's no secret that learning without motivation is ineffective. Students' interest in literature and poetry is very high in any era, therefore, to increase the motivation of students, artistic texts can be used as authentic teaching material.

According to the research of psychologists A. K. Markova and A. B. Orlov, "the motivational sphere has several aspects in its composition – a number of motives: ideals and value orientations, needs and cognitive interests. Familiarization with cultural materials helps to awaken cognitive motivation, that is, students not only master the program material, but also get acquainted with unknown cultural facts, which undoubtedly arouses their interest. Therefore, the learning process, taking into account the interests of students, becomes especially effective. From all that has been said, it follows that while maintaining interest in language as a means of communication, it is necessary to develop interest in it as a carrier of a peculiar culture. And the use of the cultural and spiritual heritage of the country of the language being studied can provide important assistance in this regard. And, of course, these may be the best examples of prose and poetry of the studied language as its meaningful component" [4, p. 43].

Thirdly, the works of art reflect the culture and spiritual values of the Russian people. Teaching a foreign language based on familiarization of students with the culture of the people of another country is one of the basic principles of teaching this subject. Familiarization with the culture of another nation, as experience shows, makes learning a foreign language more attractive.

"An artistic text is three times a cultural object. Firstly, fiction reflects the whole life of the people, including culture as its most important component. Secondly, language, the material from which an artistic text is made, is one of the

most important cultural phenomena. Finally, thirdly, an artistic text as a work of art is itself an artifact of culture" [5, p. 40].

Thus, by including the study of fiction in the curriculum, we develop the following skills of students: such as knowledge of the lexical stock of various levels (both literary words and slang), knowledge of grammar in an expanded volume, knowledge of the necessary regional and cultural information obtained from authentic texts, the ability to communicate with native speakers of a foreign language through various communication styles, the ability to read authentic texts of a given language using different types of reading, and extract information from texts in accordance with the communicative tasks of the types of reading (types of reading: viewing, studying and familiarization) and mastering the skills of writing.

The practical purpose of teaching a foreign language in classes with philology students is oral and written language proficiency within the boundaries close to the level of proficiency of native speakers of this language, the acquisition of knowledge about the language system and the ability to use this knowledge in the future professional activity of a teacher or translator.

By touching the masterpieces of Russian literature, the student achieves all the goals in learning the language. "The purpose of teaching a foreign language is a pre-planned result of language acquisition activities achieved using various techniques, methods and means of teaching" [6, p. 20].

Moreover, one of the goals of the Russian language teaching methodology is educational. According to A. N. Shchukin, learning the Russian language has great educational significance, which is manifested in the formation of the personality of students, the development of a sense of solidarity, friendship and mutual understanding between peoples. The formation of an active life position is considered as an important task to be solved in the process of implementing an educational goal [6, p. 24], including when using works of art as educational material.

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